

Influence of the Biofield Energy Treated Novel Test Formulation on Different Organ Specific Biomarkers

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Abstract

The study aimed to evaluate the effect of the Biofield Energy Treated test formulation on the function of different vital organs *viz.* bones, heart, liver, lungs, and brain in multiple cell-based assays. The test formulation and the cell media was divided into two parts; one part was untreated (UT) and other part received the Biofield Energy Treatment remotely by a renowned Biofield Energy Healer, Lauree Ann Duprey-Reed, Canada and was labeled as the Biofield Energy Treated (BT) test formulation/media. Cell viability data suggested that the test formulation was safe and non-toxic in nature in six different cells. The experimental groups of untreated medium (UT-Med) + Biofield Treated Test Item (BT-TI), BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups showed 81.1% (at 1µg/mL), 78.4% (at 63µg/mL), and 87.9% (at 63µg/mL) restoration of cell viability, respectively in human cardiac fibroblasts cells (HCF) compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Moreover, the UT-Med+ BT-TI group showed 80.4% and 89.9% restoration of cell viability at 0.1 and 1 µg/mL, respectively in human hepatoma cells (HepG2) compared to untreated. Furthermore, 181.3%, 93.2%, and 90.7% restoration of cell viability was observed in adenocarcinomic human alveolar basal epithelial cells (A549) by BT-Med + BT-TI group at 0.1, 25, and 63 µg/mL, respectively compared to the untreated. The alkaline phosphatase (ALP) level was significantly increased by 102.6%, 80.5%, and 100.5% in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively at 10µg/mL in human bone osteosarcoma cells (MG-63) compared to the untreated. Additionally, the level of ALP was significantly increased by 40% (at 10µg/mL) in the BT-Med + BT-TI group in human endometrial adenocarcinoma cells (Ishikawa) compared to the untreated. The percent protection of HCF (heart) cells (decreased of LDH activity) was significantly increased by 156.2%, 80.1%, and 137.0% in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively at 0.1µg/mL compared to the untreated in HCF cells. The percent protection of HepG2 (liver) cells (decreased of ALT activity) was significantly increased by 57.1% and 105.0% in the UT-Med + BT-TI and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively at 25 µg/mL compared to untreated in HepG2 cells. The percent protection of A549 (lungs) cells (increased of SOD activity) was significantly increased by 30.4% and 51.9% in the BT-Med + BT-TI group at 30 and 63 µg/mL, respectively compared to untreated in A549 cells. Serotonin level was significantly increased by 67.9% and 42.3% in the BT-Med + UT-TI and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively at 0.1µg/mL as compared to untreated in human neuroblastoma cells (SH-SY5Y). The relative quantification (RQ) of vitamin D receptor (VDR) was significantly increased by 136.8%, 191.9%, and 165.8% in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively at 50 µg/mL compared to the untreated in MG-63 cells. Overall, the study outcomes suggest that the Biofield Energy Treated novel proprietary test formulation significantly improved the vital functional enzyme biomarkers relevant to bones, heart, liver, lungs, and brain. Altogether data suggest that the Biofield Energy Treatment (The Trivedi Effect®) can be useful to protect and maintain the normal function of each vital organ such as lungs, liver, heart, brain,

and bones. Therefore, The Trivedi Effect® can be used as a complementary and alternative therapy against several disorders such as coronary artery disease, heart attack, heart failure, arrhythmias, congenital heart disease, cirrhosis, cardiomyopathy, liver cancer, Wilson disease, hemochromatosis, pneumonia, asthma, chronic bronchitis, emphysema, osteoporosis, cystic fibrosis, etc.

Keywords: Biofield Energy Treatment; The Trivedi Effect®; Bone health; Cardiac health; Liver health; Lungs health; VDR receptor; Brain health

Abbreviations: WHO: World Health Organization; VDR: Vitamin D Receptor; RQ: Relative Quantification; ROS: Reactive Oxygen Species; RNS: Reactive Nitrogen Species; COPD: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease; CAM: Complementary and Alternative Medicine; SOD: Superoxide Dismutase

Introduction

Bones, heart, liver, lungs, and brain disorders are the major concern of human overall health across the globe. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates, in 2016, ~17.5 million people die due to cardiovascular (heart) disorders, ~3.5 million people die due to lungs disorders, ~1.3 million people die due to liver disorders around the globe each year [1]. Moreover, ~1.2 million people most frequently diagnosed adult-onset brain disorders in each year in the USA [2]. Three main criteria to keep a healthy heart include the opening blood vessels, strengthening the heart muscle, and controlling free radical damage by antioxidants [3]. The release of liver mitochondrial enzymes is considered strong evidence for hepatic (liver) necrosis, which is associated with an increased production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) that leads to hepatic lipid peroxidation [4-6]. Oxidative stress in the respiratory system increases the production of mediators of pulmonary inflammation and initiate or promote mechanisms of carcinogenesis [7]. The lung is one of the major organs, which is highly exposed by various oxidants i.e., endogenous and exogenous oxidants (cigarette smoke, mineral dust, ozone, and radiation). These oxidants produce free radicals, while reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) are produced by phagocytes as well as by alveolar, polymorphonuclear, bronchial and different endothelial cells [8]. However, the role of oxidative stress in the pathogenesis of lung diseases has been widely reported such as asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), lung malignancies and parenchymal lung diseases like idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis and lung granulomatous diseases [9]. Serotonin (5-hydroxytryptamine, 5-HT) is among the brain's neuromodulators responsible for behavior and understanding [10]. Apart from medicines, non-pharmacologic methods that can increase serotonin by increasing recognition and happiness and well-being.

These factors can protect against mental and physical disorders [11]. There is currently no universally accepted test formulation, which improve the organ health biomarkers. With this respect, the novel test formulation was designed on the basis of best scientific literature, which is the combination of herbal products *viz.* panax ginseng extract and beta carotene, minerals *viz.* calcium chloride, magnesium gluconate, zinc chloride, sodium selenate, ferrous sulfate, and vitamins *viz.* vitamin B₁₂, vitamin D₃, ascorbic acid, and vitamin B₆. This formulation is designed for overall functioning of the organs that can results in improved overall health conditions against many pathological conditions such as lung disorder, liver disorder, breast cancer, liver cancer, aging, muscle damage, and overall health. Minerals and vitamins present in the test formulation provide significant functional support to all the vital organs [12-14]. In addition, panax ginseng is one of the best reported medicinal plants that improve mental, physical abilities, cognitive health, and is potent immunomodulation [15,16].

Various study data suggested the effect of Energy Therapy in cancer patients through therapeutic touch massage therapy [17,18] etc. Complementary and Alternative Medicine (CAM) therapies are preferred model of treatment, among which Biofield Therapy (or Healing Modalities) is one approach to enhance emotional, mental, physical, and human wellness. The National Center of Complementary and Integrative Health (NCCIH) has recognized and allowed Biofield Energy Healing as a CAM approach in addition to other therapies and medicines such as natural products, chiropractic/osteopathic manipulation, Qi Gong, deep breathing, Tai Chi, yoga, meditation, massage, special diets, healing touch, relaxation techniques, traditional Chinese herbs and medicines, naturopathy, movement therapy, homeopathy, progressive relaxation, guided imagery, pilates, acupuncture, acupressure, Reiki, rolfing structural integration, hypnotherapy, Ayurvedic medicine, mindfulness, essential oils, aromatherapy, and cranial sacral therapy. The Human Biofield Energy has subtle energy that has the capacity to work in an effective manner [19]. CAM therapies have been practiced worldwide with reported clinical benefits in different

health disease profiles [20]. This energy can be harnessed and transmitted by the practitioners into living and non-living things *via* the process of Biofield Energy Healing. The Biofield Energy Treatment, the Trivedi Effect®, has been reported to have a significant impact in the field of cancer research [21,22], materials science [23,24], microbiology [25,26], agriculture [27,28], nutraceuticals [29,30], and biotechnology [31,32]. Further, the Trivedi Effect® also significantly improved bioavailability of various low bioavailable compounds [33-35], an improved overall skin health [36,37], bone health [38-40], human health and wellness. Based on the excellent outcomes of the Biofield Energy Therapy in wide spectrum of areas, the authors intend to see the impact of the Biofield Energy Healing Treated test formulation on the function of vital organs such as bones, heart, liver, lungs, and brain specific biomarkers in different cell-lines.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals and reagents

Ferrous sulfate, vitamin B₆, vitamin D₃, vitamin B₁₂, calcium chloride, naringenin, trimetazidine (TMZ), 3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-Diphenyltetrazolium Bromide (MTT), and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) were obtained from Sigma Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO). Zinc chloride, magnesium gluconate, β-carotene, and calcitriol were purchased from TCI chemicals, Japan. Panax ginseng extract obtained from panacea Phytoextracts, India. Sodium selenate and ascorbic acid were obtained from Alfa Aesar, India. Silymarin and curcumin were obtained from Sanat Chemicals, India and quercetin obtained from Clearsynth, India. Reverse Transcription Kit, RNeasy Mini Kit, and Syber Green PCR kits were procured from Quagen, India. All the other chemicals used in this experiment were analytical grade procured from India.

Biofield energy healing strategy

The test formulation was the combination of eleven ingredients *viz.* calcium chloride, panax ginseng extract, vitamin B₁₂, β-carotene, vitamin D₃, zinc chloride, magnesium gluconate, sodium selenate, ferrous sulfate, ascorbic acid, and vitamin B₆. The test formulation and the cell media was divided into two parts; one untreated (UT) and other part received the Biofield Energy Treatment remotely by a renowned Biofield Energy Healer, Lauree Ann Duprey-Reed, under laboratory conditions for ~3 minutes through healer's unique Biofield Energy Transmission process and was labeled as the Biofield Energy Treated (BT) test formulation/media. Further, the untreated group was treated by a "sham" healer for comparison purposes. The "sham" healer did not have any knowledge about the Biofield Energy

Healing Treatment. The Biofield Energy Healer was located in the Canada, however the test items were located in the research laboratory of Dabur Research Foundation, New Delhi, India. Biofield Energy Healer in this experiment did not visit the laboratory, nor had any contact with the test samples. After that, the Biofield Energy Treated and untreated test items were kept in similar sealed conditions and used for the study as per the study plan.

Assessment of cell viability using MTT assay

Cells were counted using hemocytometer and plated in 96-well plates at the specific density described in Table 1. The cells were then incubated overnight under growth conditions to allow cell recovery and exponential growth. Following overnight incubation, cells were treated with different concentrations of test formulations (BT/UT). Following respective treatments, cells were incubated in a CO₂ incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂, and 95% humidity and incubated for time period mentioned in Table 1. After incubation, the plates were taken out and 20 μL of 5 mg/mL of MTT 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide solution was added to all the wells followed by additional incubation for 3 hours at 37°C. The supernatant was aspirated and 150 μL of DMSO was added to each well to dissolve formazan crystals. The absorbance of each well was read at 540 nm using Synergy HT microplate reader. The percentage cytotoxicity at each tested concentration of TI was calculated using Equation 1

$$\% \text{ Cytotoxicity} = [(R-X)/R] * 100 \quad (1)$$

Where, X = Absorbance of treated cells; R = Absorbance of untreated cells

The concentrations exhibiting percentage cytotoxicity < 30% was considered as non-cytotoxic [41].

S. No.	Cell Line	Plating	Time Point
1	MG-63 (Bone)	3x10 ⁴ cells/ well, 96-well plate	5 days
2	Ishikawa (Uterus)	3x10 ⁴ cells/ well, 96-well plate	5 days
3	A549 (Lung)	10x10 ⁴ cells/ well, 96-well plate	24 hours
4	HepG2 (Liver)	1x10 ⁴ cells/ well, 96-well plate	24 hours
5	Human Cardiac fibroblasts (Heart)	1x10 ⁴ cells/ well, 96-well plate	24 hours
6	SH-SY5Y (Neuronal cell)	10x10 ⁴ cells/ well, 96-well plate	24 hours

Table 1: Information related to six cell lines with their plating density and time-point.

Evaluation of the cytoprotective effect of the formulation

Cells (human cardiac fibroblasts-HCF; human hepatoma cells-HepG2; and adenocarcinomic human alveolar basal epithelial cells-A549) were counted and plated in suitable medium followed by overnight incubation. The cells were then treated with the test items/positive control at the non-cytotoxic concentrations for 24 hours. After 24 hours, oxidative stress was given to the cells using 10 mM *t*-BHP for 3.5 hours. The untreated cells served as a control that did not receive any treatment and was maintained in cell growth medium only. Cells treated with 10 mM of *t*-BHP alone served as negative control. After 3.5 hours of incubation with *t*-BHP the above plates were taken out and cell viability was determined by MTT assay. The percentage protection corresponding to each treatment was calculated using Equation 2:

$$\% \text{ Protection} = \frac{[(\text{Absorbance}_{\text{sample}} - \text{Absorbance}_{t\text{-BHP}})] * 100}{[\text{Absorbance}_{\text{untreated}} - \text{Absorbance}_{t\text{-BHP}}]} \quad (2)$$

Assessment of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity

The cells (human bone osteosarcoma cells-MG-63 and human endometrial adenocarcinoma cells-Ishikawa) were counted using a hemocytometer and plated in 24-well plates at the density corresponding to 1×10^4 cells/well in phenol-free DMEM supplemented with 10% CD-FBS. Following the respective treatments, the cells in the above plate were incubated for 48 hours in CO₂ incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂, and 95% humidity. After 48 hours of incubation, the plates were taken out and processed for the measurement of ALP enzyme activity. The cells were washed with 1 X PBS and lysed by freeze-thaw method *i.e.*, incubation at -80°C for 20 minutes followed by incubation at 37°C for 10 minutes. To the lysed cells, 50 µL of substrate solution *i.e.*, 5 mM of *p*-nitrophenyl phosphate (*p*NPP) in 1M diethanolamine and 0.24 mM magnesium chloride (MgCl₂) solution (pH 10.4) was added to all the wells followed by incubation for 1 hour at 37°C. The absorbance of the above solution was read at 405 nm using Synergy HT microplate reader (Biotek, USA). The absorbance values obtained were normalized with substrate blank (*p*NPP solution alone) absorbance values. The percentage increase in ALP enzyme activity with respect to the untreated cells (baseline group) was calculated using Equation 3:

$$\% \text{ Increase in ALP} = \{(X-R)/R\} * 100 \quad (3)$$

Where, X = Absorbance of cells corresponding to positive control and test groups

R = Absorbance of cells corresponding to baseline group (untreated cells)

Estimation of lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) in human cardiac fibroblasts (HCF)

The human cardiac fibroblasts (HCF) Cells were counted and plated at the density of 0.25×10^6 cells/ well in 24-well plates in cardiac fibroblast specific medium followed by overnight incubation. The cells were then treated with the test formulation/positive control at the non-cytotoxic concentrations for 24 hours. After 24 hours, oxidative stress was given to the cells using 10 mM *t*-BHP for 3.5 hours. The untreated cells were served as control that did not receive any treatment and were maintained in cell growth medium only. Cells treated with 10 mM of *t*-BHP alone served as the negative control. After 3.5 hours of incubation with *t*-BHP the above plates were taken out and LDH activity was determined using LDH activity kit as per manufacturer's instructions. The percent increase in LDH activity was calculated using Equation 4.

$$\% \text{ Increase} = \frac{[(\text{LDH activity}_{\text{sample}} - \text{LDH activity}_{t\text{-BHP}})] * 100}{[\text{LDH activity}_{\text{untreated}} - \text{LDH activity}_{t\text{-BHP}}]} \quad (4)$$

Estimation of ALT in liver cells (HepG2)

The human hepatoma cells (HepG2) were counted and plated at the density of 5×10^4 cells/well in 48-well plates in DMEM media followed by overnight incubation. The cells were then treated with the test formulation/positive control at the non-cytotoxic concentrations for 24 hours. After 24 hours, oxidative stress was given to the cells using 400µM *t*-BHP for 3.5 hours. The untreated cells served as control that did not receive any treatment and were maintained in cell growth medium only. Cells treated with 400 µM of *t*- BHP alone served as negative control. After 3.5 hours of incubation with *t*-BHP the above plates were taken out and ALT activity was determined using ALT activity kit as per manufacturer's instructions. The percent increase in ALT activity was calculated using Equation 5.

$$\% \text{ Increase} = \frac{[(\text{ALT activity}_{\text{sample}} - \text{ALT activity}_{t\text{-BHP}})] * 100}{[\text{ALT activity}_{\text{untreated}} - \text{ALT activity}_{t\text{-BHP}}]} \quad (5)$$

Estimation of superoxide dismutase (SOD) in lung (A549) cells

The adenocarcinomic human alveolar basal epithelial cells (A549) were counted and plated at the density of 1×10^4 cells/well in 24-well plates in DMEM followed by overnight incubation. The cells were then treated with the test formulation/ positive control at the non-cytotoxic concentrations along with 100 µM *t*-BHP to induce oxidative stress. The untreated cells served as control that did not receive any treatment and were maintained in cell growth medium only. Cells treated with 100 µM of *t*-BHP alone served as negative control. After 24 hours of

incubation with *t*-BHP the above plates were taken out and SOD activity was determined using SOD activity kit as per manufacturer's instructions. The percent increase in SOD activity was calculated using Equation 6:

$$\% \text{ Increase in SOD activity} = ((X-R)/R)*100 \quad (6)$$

Where, X = SOD activity corresponding to Test Item or Positive Control

R = SOD activity corresponding to Control group.

Estimation of serotonin in neuronal cells (SH-SY5Y)

The human neuroblastoma (SH-SY5Y) cells were counted and plated at the density of 10×10^4 cells/well in 96-well plates followed by overnight incubation. The cells were then treated with the test items/positive control at the non-cytotoxic concentrations. The untreated cells served as control that did not receive any treatment and were maintained in cell growth medium only. The treated cells were incubated for 24 hours. Serotonin release was determined by ELISA as per manufacturer's protocol. The percent increase in serotonin levels was calculated using Equation 7.

$$[(X-R)/R]*100 \quad (7)$$

Where, X = Serotonin levels corresponding to test item or positive control

R = Serotonin levels corresponding to control group.

Effect of test formulation on vitamin D receptor (VDR) in bone (MG-63) cells

The human bone osteosarcoma (MG-63) cells were counted using the hemocytometer were plated at a density of 2×10^5 cells/well in 6-well plates followed by overnight incubation. The cells were then sera starved for 24 hours and treated with the test formulation/positive control at the non-cytotoxic concentrations. The untreated cells that served as control that did not receive any treatment and were maintained in cell growth medium only. The treated cells were incubated for 24 hours and VDR expression was determined by Q-PCR using VDR specific primers. Cells were harvested by scrapping and washed with PBS. Cell pellets obtained were analyzed for VDR gene expression using human VDR specific primers: Forward: 5'-GCTGACCTGGTCAGTTACAGCA-3', Reverse: 5'-CACGTCAGTACGCGGTACTT-3'. VDR gene expression was normalized using House-keeping (HK) reference. Relative quantification (RQ) of VDR gene in Biofield

Energy Treated cells was calculated with respect to the untreated cells using Equation 8:

$$RQ = 2^{-N} \quad (8)$$

Where N is the relative Threshold Cycle (CT) value of treated sample with respect to the untreated sample.

Results and Discussion

Cell viability using MTT assay

Determination of non-cytotoxic concentration of the test formulation (untreated and Biofield Energy Treated) and positive controls by MTT cell viability assay was used in terms of percent viable cells in six (6) cell-lines *viz.* MG-63, Ishikawa, A549, HepG2, HCF, and SH-SY5Y. As per the percent cell viability data, it was observed that the test formulation and positive controls were safe and non-toxic at the tested concentrations in six different cell lines and further selected for other parameters analysis.

Evaluation of cytoprotective effect of the test formulation

For the evaluation of the vital organs *viz.* heart, liver, and lungs of the formulation was examined in *in vitro* cell-based assay under the stimulation of *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*-BHP) induced oxidative stress. *t*-BHP has been routinely used for the induction of oxidative stress in various cells [41,42]. The cytoprotective effect of the Consciousness Energy Treated test formulation on the restoration of cell viability was evaluated against *t*-BHP induced cell damage (Figure 1). Trimetazidine (TMZ) was used as positive control in human cardiac fibroblasts cells (HCF) and showed, restoration of cell viability by 56.61%, 94.09%, and 102.29% at 5, 10, and 25 μ g/mL, respectively than *t*-BHP induced group. The test formulation showed 81.1% restoration of cell viability at 1 μ g/mL in the UT-Med + BT-TI group as compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Moreover, at 10 μ g/mL the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups showed 12%, 12.8%, and 66.4% restoration of cell viability, respectively than UT-Med + UT-TI group. Additionally, the test formulation showed 42.3%, 78.4%, and 87.9% restoration of cell viability at 25 μ g/mL in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively than UT-Med + UT-TI group. Further, at 63 μ g/mL the test formulation showed 49.1% restoration of cell viability in the BT-Med + BT-TI group than UT-Med + UT-TI group (Figure 1). Silymarin was used as positive control in human hepatoma cells (HepG2) resulted, restoration of cell viability by 38.79%, 73.92%, and 81.74% at 5, 10 and 25 μ g/mL, respectively compared to the *t*-BHP induced group. Besides, the test formulation showed 80.4%,

89.9%, and 22.6% restoration of cell viability at 0.1, 1, and 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively in the UT-Med + BT-TI group as compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Moreover, at 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ the UT-Med + BT-TI and BT-Med + UT-TI groups showed 39.5% and 13% restoration of cell viability than UT-Med + UT-TI group. Additionally, at 63 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ the test formulation showed 25.1%, 15.3%, and 16.5% restoration of cell viability in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively as compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group (Figure 1). Quercetin was used as positive control in adenocarcinomic human alveolar basal epithelial cells (A549) resulted, restoration of cell viability by 31%, 41.93%, and 55.74% at 1, 10 and 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively compared to the *t*-BHP induced group. Besides, the test formulation showed 46.1% and 181.3% restoration of cell viability at 0.1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in the BT-Med + UT-TI and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Moreover, at 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ the BT-Med + UT-TI and BT-Med + BT-TI groups

showed 10.8% and 35.8% restoration of cell viability, respectively than UT-Med + UT-TI group. Additionally, the test formulation showed 80.6%, 93.2%, and 93.2% restoration of cell viability at 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Further, the test formulation showed 82%, 83.7%, and 90.7% restoration of cell viability at 63 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group (Figure 1). The cellular antioxidant capacity can reduce due to excess production of free radicals that can affect the normal functions of cell membrane and leads to inflammation [43,44]. The results indicated that the addition of Biofield Treatment has significantly protects *t*-BHP induced cardiotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, and lung cell toxicities, which could be due to The Trivedi Effect®-Biofield Energy Healing.

Figure 1: Assessment of cytoprotective effect of the test formulation in human cardiac fibroblasts cells (HCF), human hepatoma cells (HepG2), and adenocarcinomic human alveolar basal epithelial cells (A549) against *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*-BHP) induced damage. TMZ: Trimetazidine (μM), silymarin ($\mu\text{g/mL}$), and quercetin (μM) were used as positive control in HCF, HepG2, and A549 cells, respectively. UT: Untreated; Med: Medium; BT: Biofield Treated; TI: Test item.

Assessment of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity

The effect of the test formulation on bone-specific alkaline phosphatase level is shown in Figure 2. The positive control, calcitriol showed 24.82%, 33.70%, and 62.95% increase the level of ALP at 0.1, 1, and 10 nM, respectively in MG-63 cells. Moreover, the experimental groups showed 102.6%, 80.5%, and 100.5% increase the level of ALP in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively with respect to the UT-Med + UT-TI group at 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. At 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, the percent ALP was significantly increased by 86.7%, 82.8%, and 87.1% in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med +

BT-TI groups, respectively compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group (Figure 2). Besides, the positive control naringenin showed 39.43%, 88.45%, and 113.64% increase the level of ALP at 1, 5, and 10 nM, respectively in Ishikawa cells. ALP percent was significantly increased by 12.5% and 16.3% in the UT-Med + BT-TI and BT-Med + UT-TI groups, respectively compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group at 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Moreover, the experimental groups showed 9.3% and 40.7% increase the level of ALP in the BT-Med + UT-TI and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively with respect to the UT-Med + UT-TI group at 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. At 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, the percent ALP was significantly increased by 23.5% in the BT-Med + UT-TI group compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group (Figure 2). Bone alkaline phosphatase

(ALP) is a tetrameric glycoprotein present on the cell surface of osteoblast cells and it is essential for the bone mineralization and considered as a useful biochemical marker for bone formation [45,46]. Thus, measurement of bone specific biochemical marker in serum can be clinically useful in evaluating the progress of the bone

healing process [47,48]. In this experiment, the level of ALP was revealed that the Biofield Energy Healing Treated test formulation significantly increased the level of ALP expression, which might be very helpful to the patients suffering from various bone-related anomalies.

Figure 2: Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity of the test formulation on A. Human bone osteosarcoma cells (MG-63) and B. Human endometrial adenocarcinoma cells (Ishikawa). Calcitriol and naringenin were used as positive control in Mg-63 and Ishikawa cells, respectively. UT: Untreated; Med: Medium; BT: Biofield Treated; TI: Test item.

Estimation of lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity in human cardiac fibroblasts (HCF)

The lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) enzyme is mainly present in the heart and skeletal muscle, and responsible for anaerobic respiration of cells [49]. In most of the coronary vascular disease (CVD) cases there are massive alteration of LDH isozyme [50]. The percent protection of HCF cells in terms of decreased level of lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity after treatment with the test formulation is shown in Figure 3. The positive control, trimetazidine (TMZ) exhibited 3.59%, 30.14%, and 69.42% protection of HCF cells (decreased of LDH activity) compared to the *t*-BHP group. The percent protection of HCF cells (decreased of LDH activity) was significantly increased by 156.2%, 80.1%, and 137.0% in

the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively at 0.1 µg/mL as compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Moreover, at 1 µg/mL, the percent protection of HCF cells (decreased of LDH activity) was significantly increased by 35.8%, 41.1%, and 62.6% in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively as compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group (Figure 3). The study observation signify that there was a significant reduction of LDH level after Biofield Energy Treatment and protect heart cells, which might be helpful to resist against various pathological conditions like hemolysis or malignancies, tissue injury, necrosis, hypoxia, etc. It also indicating that the heart cells acted normally under stress and anaerobic condition and improved overall heart function.

Figure 3: The percent protection of HCF cells in terms of decreased lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity against *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*-BHP) induced damage after treatment with the test formulation. TMZ: Trimetazidine; UT: Untreated; Med: Medium; BT: Biofield Treated; TI: Test item.

Estimation of alanine amino transferase (ALT) activity in HepG2 cells

Protection of HepG2 cells after treatment of the test formulation on in terms of decrease alanine amino transferase (ALT) activity is shown in Figure 4. The positive control, silymarin exhibited 6.52%, 74.51%, and 106.27% protection of HepG2 cells (decreased of ALT activity). The protection of HepG2 cells (decreased of ALT activity) was significantly increased by 26.1% at 1 µg/mL in the BT-Med + BT-TI group as compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Moreover, at 10 µg/mL, percent protection of HepG2 cells (decreased of ALT activity) was increased by 42.6%, 35.1%, and 49.3% in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively as compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Further, protection of HepG2 cells (decreased of ALT activity) was also significantly increased by 57.1%, 22.1%, and 105.0%

in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively at 25 µg/mL as compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group (Figure 4). Most of drug metabolism takes place largely in the liver; however, the overproduction of reactive oxygen species (ROS) during metabolisms causes hepatocellular damage [51]. Based on the preclinical safety assessment studies, alanine aminotransferase (ALT) has been routinely used as a hepatic biomarker [52]. It also plays a significant role in gluconeogenesis and amino acid metabolism and increase response due to dietary protein, during fasting, and in diabetic animals [53]. Here, the Biofield Energy Treatment significantly protects liver hepatocytes in terms of reducing the level of transaminases enzyme, ALT as compared to the *t*-BHP inducing group, which might be due to the Consciousness Energy Healing Treatment to the test formulation.

Figure 4: Effect of the test formulation on the percent protection of human liver cancer (HepG2) cells in terms of decreased alanine amino transaminase (ALT) activity under the stimulation of *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*-BHP). UT: Untreated; Med: Medium; BT: Biofield Treated; TI: Test item.

Measurement of superoxide dismutase (SOD)

The protection of lungs cells (A549) in terms of increased super oxide dismutase (SOD) activity after treatment with the test formulation is shown in Figure 5. The positive control, showed 80.67%, 97.01%, and 109.56% protection of A549 (lungs) cells (increased of SOD activity) compared to the *t*-BHP group. The percent protection of A549 (lungs) cells (increased of SOD activity) was significantly increased by 13.3% and 30.4% at 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in the UT-Med + BT-TI and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Moreover, at 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, the percent protection of A549 (lungs) cells (increased of SOD activity) was significantly increased by 14.4% and 7.1% in the BT-Med + UT-TI and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively as compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Further, the percent protection of A549 (lungs) cells (increased of SOD

activity) was significantly increased by 29.3% and 51.9% in the BT-Med + UT-TI and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively at 63 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ as compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group (Figure 5). Several molecular mechanisms already been proved that excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation causes inflammation and cellular damage that ultimately leads to pathogenesis of sepsis [54]. The main sources of ROS in the lung during sepsis are inflammatory cells and mitochondria. Production of ROS leads to lipid, protein, and extracellular matrix damage, which increases pulmonary inflammation [55]. Altogether, data indicated a significant increased SOD level after Biofield Energy Treatment in A549 cells, which might be helpful to resist against various pathological conditions like oxidative stress and related adverse-effect. It also indicating that the lung cells acted normally and improved overall respiratory activities.

Figure 5: Effect of the test formulation on the percent protection of lungs cells (A549) in terms of increased SOD activity under the stimulation of *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*-BHP). UT: Untreated; Med: Medium; BT: Biofield Treated; TI: Test item.

Serotonin level in human neuroblastoma (SH-SY5Y) cells

Serotonin level was measured in SH-SY5Y cells by ELISA and the data are shown in Figure 6. The positive control, showed 98.2%, 123.53%, and 156.76% increase the level of serotonin at 0.1, 1, and 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. The level of serotonin was significantly increased by 13.1%, 67.9%, and 42.3% in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI group at 0.1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Moreover, at 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 5-HT level was significantly increased by 25.6%, 35%, and 37.7% in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively as compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Further, the serotonin level was significantly increased by 34.1%, 38.3%, and 43.6% in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups,

respectively at 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ as compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group (Figure 6). Serotonin (5-HT) is one of the best modulatory neurotransmitters with both presynaptic release and postsynaptic reception function. It plays a wide variety of brain functions, *viz.* autonomic regulation, sensory perception, neurodevelopment, feeding and motor function to emotional regulation and cognition [56]. Deficiency of 5-HT leads to various neuropsychiatric disorders like Alzheimer's disease, depression, memory loss, loss of ability of thinking, cognitive health, etc. [57]. Thus, the data suggested that Biofield Treated novel formulation has significantly improved the level of serotonin, which would be highly useful against various neurodegenerative diseases and other age-related disorders and an improved the normal functioning of the brain tissues.

Figure 6: Effect of the test formulation on percent increase in 5-hydroxy tryptamine (5-HT) or serotonin in human neuroblastoma cells (SH-SY5Y). UT: Untreated; Med: Medium; BT: Biofield Treated; TI: Test item.

Effect of test formulation on vitamin D receptors (VDRs)

Human bone osteosarcoma cells (MG-63) were treated with the test formulation and the effect on VDR expression was determined using quantitative-polymerase chain reaction (Q-PCR) amplification. VDR-relative threshold cycle (VDR-CT) values were obtained from PCR amplification. Relative quantification (RQ) was determined from the VDR-CT and house-keeping (HK)-CT values in MG-63 cells is represented in Figure 7. The positive control (calcitriol) showed 61.33%, 107.05%, and 160.27% increase of RQ of VDR at 1, 10, and 100 nM, respectively. Moreover, RQ of VDR was significantly increased by 22.1%, 61%, and 95.6% in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively at 1 μg/mL compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Additionally, at 10 μg/mL the VDR level was significantly increased by 15.5%, 134.6%, and 115.7% in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI

groups, respectively compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Further, VDR level was also significantly increased by 136.8%, 191.9%, and 165.8% in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively at 50 μg/mL compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. After binding the active form of vitamin D to the VDR that prevent the release of calcium in serum [58]. Common allelic variations in the vitamin D receptor (VDR) gene alter bone density. Bone density is an important predictor of osteoporotic fracture risk, affected by hormonal and environmental factors [59]. Overexpression of VDR in osteoblasts and osteocytes prevents bone loss during vitamin D-deficiency [60]. Overall, the Biofield Treated novel formulation has significantly increased the expression of VDRs, which might be very helpful to bind more active vitamin D₃ metabolites and can improve the more physiological functions of vitamin D and improved bone cell growth and development.

Figure 7: Effect of the test formulation on percent increase in relative quantification (RQ) of vitamin D receptors (VDRs) gene in human bone osteosarcoma cells (MG-63). UT: Untreated; Med: Medium; BT: Biofield Treated; TI: Test item.

Conclusion

The study results showed that the tested novel test formulation was non-toxic and safe based on MTT cell viability assay in six tested cells. The treatment groups like UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups showed 81.1%, 78.4%, and 87.9% restoration of cell viability at 1, 63, and 63 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively in human cardiac fibroblasts cells (HCF) compared to the UT-Med + UT-TI group. Moreover, the UT-Med + BT-TI group showed 80.4% (0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and 89.9% (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) restoration of cell viability in human hepatoma cells (HepG2) compared to the untreated group. Additionally, the BT-Med + BT-TI group showed 181.3%, 93.2%, and 90.7% restoration of cell viability at 0.1, 25, and 63 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively in adenocarcinomic human alveolar basal epithelial cells (A549) compared to the untreated group. Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity was significantly increased by 102.6%, 80.5%, and 100.5% UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively at 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in human bone osteosarcoma cells (MG-63) compared to the untreated in human bone osteosarcoma cells (MG-63). The percent protection of HCF cells (decreased of LDH activity) was significantly increased by 156.2% and 137% in the UT-Med + BT-TI and BT-Med + BT-TI groups, respectively at 0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ compared to the untreated group in HCF cells. The percent protection of HepG2 cells (decreased of ALT activity) was significantly increased by 105% (at 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) compared to the untreated group in HepG2 cells. The percent protection of A549 (lungs) cells (increased of SOD activity) was significantly increased by 51.9% in the BT-Med + BT-TI group at 63 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ compared to the untreated group in A549 cells. The serotonin level was significantly increased by 67.9% at 0.1 in the BT-Med + BT-TI group compared to the untreated group in human neuroblastoma cells (SH-SY5Y). The relative quantification (RQ) of vitamin D receptors (VDRs) level was significantly increased by 136.8%, 191.9%, and 165.8% in the UT-Med + BT-TI, BT-Med + UT-TI, and BT-Med + BT-TI, respectively at the concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ than untreated in MG-63 cells. In conclusion, The Biofield Energy Treatment significantly improved heart, liver, bones, neuronal, and lungs functional enzymes and also protected cardiomyocyte, hepatocyte, osteocytes, pneumocyte, and nerve cells from oxidative damage induced by *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*-BHP). Thus, results suggested that Biofield Energy Treatment could be utilized for the prevention of different types of cardiac disorders (peripheral artery disease, high blood pressure, congenital heart disease, stroke, congestive heart failure, rheumatic heart disease, carditis, valvular heart disease, thromboembolic disease, and venous thrombosis, etc.), hepatic disorders (cirrhosis,

Wilson disease, liver cancer, hemochromatosis), and lungs disorders (Asthma, Emphysema, Chronic bronchitis, Pneumonia, Cystic fibrosis). Further, it could be used to improve normal cell growth and differentiation, cell-to-cell messaging, neurotransmission, cell cycling and proliferation, hormonal balance, skin health, immune and cardiovascular functions. Moreover, it could also be utilized in various organ transplants (i.e., heart, liver, and kidney transplants), aging, and various inflammatory and immune-related disease conditions like Ulcerative Colitis (UC), Alzheimer's Disease (AD), Hashimoto Thyroiditis, Dermatitis, Asthma, Pernicious Anemia, Sjogren Syndrome, Aplastic Anemia, Multiple Sclerosis, Hepatitis, Graves' Disease, Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS), Dermatomyositis, Diabetes, Myasthenia Gravis, Atherosclerosis, Parkinson's Disease, Systemic etc. to Lupus Erythematosus (SLE), stress, improve overall health and Quality of Life.

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